

Chirality transitions in a system of active flat spinners. Supplementary Material

Miguel A. López-Castaño^a, Alejandro Márquez Seco^a, Alicia Márquez Seco^a, Álvaro Rodríguez-Rivas^b, and Francisco Vega Reyes^{a,*}

^aDepartamento de Física and Instituto de Computación Científica Avanzada (ICCAEx), Universidad de Extremadura, 06071 Badajoz, Spain; ^bDepartment of Physical, Chemical and Natural Systems, Pablo de Olavide University, 41013, Sevilla, Spain; *fvega@eaphysics.xyz

1 **Supplementary Material file with theoretical methods and additional experiments figures, movies description and data.**

Particle velocity distribution function. Characterization of statistical correlations

Due to the inherent symmetries observed in the experiments, the particle distribution function should display the following features:

- Particle spin is of the form $\mathbf{w} = w_z \hat{\mathbf{e}}_z$, with w_z either positive or negative.
- Although $f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w})$ is not isotropic, but its anisotropies would rise only through the coupling of \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} ; i.e., through $\cos \alpha \equiv \langle (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{w}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_\phi / |\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{w}| \rangle$ since experimental results indicate that X, Y axes are indistinguishable.
- $f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w})$ is sensitive to the sign of $\cos \alpha$; since $\cos \alpha < 0$ the particle spin-velocity correlation is clockwise and when $\cos \alpha > 0$ the particle spin-velocity correlation is counter clockwise.

We denote the single particle distribution function, as $f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w})$, where r is the particle distance from the system center, \mathbf{v} is the particle velocity and \mathbf{w} the particle spin (angular velocity).

The marginal distribution functions, used in Figure 1 are defined as

$$f_{r,w}(v) = \int (1/n(r)) dr \int d\mathbf{w} f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) \delta(|\mathbf{v} - v|). \quad f_{r,v}(w) = \int (1/n(r)) dr \int d\mathbf{v} f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) \delta(w_z - w), \quad [1]$$

where $n(r)$ is the particle density field. The relevant fields, particle density $n(r)$, flow velocity $\mathbf{u}(r)$, particle angular momentum $\mathbf{\Omega}(r)$ are defined as

$$n(r) = \int d\mathbf{v} \int d\mathbf{w} f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}), \quad \mathbf{u}(r) = (1/n(r)) \int d\mathbf{v} \int d\mathbf{w} f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) \mathbf{v}, \quad \mathbf{\Omega}(r) = (1/n(r)) \int d\mathbf{v} \int d\mathbf{w} f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) \mathbf{w} \quad [2]$$

and average kinetic energies T_t (translational) and T_r (rotational)

$$T_t(r) = \frac{m}{2n(r)} \int d\mathbf{v} \int d\mathbf{w} f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}(r))^2, \quad T_r(r) = \frac{I}{2n(r)} \int d\mathbf{v} \int d\mathbf{w} f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) w^2, \quad [3]$$

with $w \equiv |\mathbf{w}| = |w_z|$ and m, I are particle mass and moment of inertia, respectively. We also define the spin thermal fluctuations

$$T_r^*(r) = \frac{I}{2n(r)} \int d\mathbf{v} \int d\mathbf{w} f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) (\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{\Omega})^2, \quad [4]$$

The scale of thermal fluctuations for translations (T_t) and rotations (T_r^*) in our system will in general be different. For convenience, we define $\mathbf{V} \equiv \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}(r)$, $\mathbf{W} \equiv \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{\Omega}(r)$; $V = (\mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{V})^{1/2}$, $W = (\mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{W})^{1/2}$. Let us also define the bivariate Maxwellian

$$f_{2M}(r, V^*, W^*) = n(r) \left(\frac{m}{2\pi T_t(r)} \right) \left(\frac{I}{2\pi T_r^*(r)} \right)^{1/2} e^{-\frac{V^2}{2T_t/m}} e^{-\frac{W^2}{2T_r^*/I}} \equiv n(r) \left(\frac{m}{2\pi T_t(r)} \right) \left(\frac{I}{2\pi T_r^*(r)} \right)^{1/2} e^{-V^{*2}} e^{-W^{*2}}. \quad [5]$$

29 Henceforth, we use the notation: $V^* = V/(2T_t/m)^{1/2} \equiv V/\langle V \rangle^{1/2}$, $W^* = W/(2T_r^*/I)^{1/2} \equiv W/\langle W^2 \rangle^{1/2}$ for j -th powers of
 30 translational velocities and angular velocities, respectively, where we have taken into account Eq. (3).

31 We can write the distribution function as a polynomial expansion around $f_{2M}(r, V^*, W^*)$.

$$\begin{aligned} f(r, V^*, W^*, \cos \alpha) &= f_{2M}(r, V^*, W^*) \sum_{j,k,\ell=0}^{\infty} a_{jk}^{(\ell)} L_j^{(\ell+\ell_0)}(V^{*2}) L_k^{(\ell+\ell'_0)}(W^{*2}) P_\ell(\cos \alpha) W(V^{*2}, V^{*2}, \cos \alpha) \\ &= n(r) \frac{m}{2T_t(r)} \left(\frac{I}{2T_r^*(r)} \right)^{1/2} \sum_{j,k,\ell=0}^{\infty} a_{jk}^{(\ell)} L_j^{(\ell+\ell_0)}(V^{*2}) L_k^{(\ell+\ell'_0)}(W^{*2}) P_\ell(\cos \alpha) (\pi^{-3/2} e^{-V^{*2}} e^{-W^{*2}}) W(V^{*2}, V^{*2}, \cos \alpha), \end{aligned} \quad [6]$$

32 where j, k, ℓ are positive integers and ℓ_0, ℓ'_0 are (integer) constants. Symbols $L_j^{(\ell)}(x)$, with ℓ being an integer, stand for the
 33 associated Laguerre polynomials of order (j, ℓ) , and with $x \in [0, \infty]$. They are also commonly denoted, in the context of kinetic
 34 theory, as Sonine polynomials (1, 2). Also, P_ℓ are the Legendre polynomials.

35 The independent variable $\cos \alpha$ characterizes particle chirality, and is defined here as

$$\cos \alpha \equiv \frac{\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{w}}{|\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{w}|} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_\phi = w_z \frac{v_y \hat{\mathbf{e}}_x - v_x \hat{\mathbf{e}}_y}{|\mathbf{v}| |\mathbf{w}|} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_\phi = \frac{w_z}{w} \left(\frac{v_y \hat{\mathbf{e}}_x - v_x \hat{\mathbf{e}}_y}{v} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{-y \hat{\mathbf{e}}_x + x \hat{\mathbf{e}}_y}{r} \right) = -\text{sg}(w_z) \frac{\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{r}}{r v} = -\text{sg}(w) \frac{v_r}{v}. \quad [7]$$

37 Notice, from Eq. (7), that determination of $\cos \alpha$ involves also knowledge of particle position and thus, it will be considered
 38 henceforth as an integration variable that is independent of reduced particle velocity (V^*) and spin (W^*).

39 The product of associated Laguerre and Legendre polynomials both configure the set of orthogonal poly-
 40 nomials $L_j^{(\ell)}(V^{*2}) L_k^{(\ell)}(W^{*2}) (V^* W^*)^{2\ell} P_\ell(\cos \alpha)$ in Eq. (6). Use of the shifted Legendre polynomials (3, 4) is
 41 not justified here since, as we said, particle chirality depends on the sign of $\cos \alpha$. The weight func-
 42 tion $W(V^{*2}, V^{*2}, \cos \alpha)$ is determined so that $\int d\mathbf{V}^* \int d\mathbf{W}^* \int d(\cos \alpha) W(V^*, W^*, \cos \alpha) (\pi^{-3/2} e^{-V^{*2}} e^{-W^{*2}} / W^*) =$
 43 $\int d\mathbf{V}^* \int d\mathbf{W}^* \int d(\cos \alpha) w_L^{(\ell)}(V^{*2}) w_L^{(\ell)}(W^{*2}) w_P(\cos \alpha)$, where $w_L^{(\ell)}(x) \equiv e^{-x} x^\ell$, $w_P(x) \equiv 1$ are the weight functions of
 44 the associated Laguerre and Legendre polynomials respectively (3), with respect to a variable x . Taking into account that
 45 $(m/2T_t(r)) \int d\mathbf{V} = \int d\mathbf{V}^* = 2\pi \int V^* dV^* = \pi \int_0^\infty dV^{*2}$, $(I/2T_r^*(r))^{1/2} \int d\mathbf{W} = 2 \int_0^\infty dW^* = \int_0^\infty (1/W^*) dW^{*2}$, we obtain
 46 $W(V^*, W^*, \cos \alpha) = \pi^{1/2} W^* (V^* W^*)^{2\ell}$.

47 Therefore, for products of the type $\left[L_j^{(\ell+\ell_0)}(V^{*2}) L_k^{(\ell+\ell'_0)}(W^{*2}) P_\ell(\cos \alpha) \right] \times f(r, V^*, W^*, \cos \alpha)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\int d\mathbf{V} \int d\mathbf{W} \int_{-1}^1 d(\cos \alpha) \left[L_j^{(\ell+\ell_0)}(V^{*2}) L_k^{(\ell+\ell'_0)}(W^{*2}) P_\ell(\cos \alpha) \right] f(r, V^*, W^*, \cos \alpha) \\ &= n(r) \sum_{j,k,\ell=0}^{\infty} \int_0^\infty dV^{*2} \int_0^\infty dW^{*2} \int_{-1}^{+1} d(\cos \alpha) \left(L_j^{(\ell)}(V^{*2}) L_k^{(\ell)}(W^{*2}) P_\ell(\cos \alpha) \right) \left(L_{j'}^{(\ell')} (V^{*2}) L_{k'}^{(\ell')} (W^{*2}) P_{\ell'}(\cos \alpha) \right) \\ &\times e^{-V^{*2}-W^{*2}} (V^* W^*)^{2\ell} \\ &= n(r) \sum_{j,k,\ell=0}^{\infty} a_{jk}^{(\ell)} \frac{\Gamma(j+\ell+1)}{j!} \frac{\Gamma(k+\ell+1)}{k!} \frac{2}{2\ell+1} \delta_{j,j'} \delta_{k,k'} \delta_{\ell,\ell'} = n(r) a_{jk}^{(\ell)} \frac{\Gamma(j+\ell+\ell_0+1)}{j!} \frac{\Gamma(k+\ell+\ell'_0+1)}{k!} \frac{2}{2\ell+1}, \end{aligned} \quad [8]$$

48 where we have taken into account the orthogonality conditions for the associated Laguerre and Legendre polynomials (3).

49 In order to determine the constants ℓ_0, ℓ'_0 we determine the integral in Eq. (8), for $j=1, k=0, \ell=0$, taking into account
 50 also Eq. (3)

$$\begin{aligned} &\int d\mathbf{V} \int d\mathbf{W} \int d(\cos \alpha) L_1^{(\ell_0)}(V^{*2}) L_0^{(\ell'_0)}(W^{*2}) P_0(\cos \alpha) f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) = \int d\mathbf{V} \int d\mathbf{W} \int d(\cos \alpha) (1 + \ell_0 - V^{*2}) f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}) \\ &= \left(1 + \ell_0 - \frac{\langle V^2 \rangle}{2T_t(r)/m} \right) n(r), \end{aligned} \quad [9]$$

51 (where we have used $\langle \dots \rangle = (1/n(r)) \int d\mathbf{V} \int d\mathbf{W} \int d(\cos \alpha) (\dots) f(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w})$) which, by comparing with Eq. (8) leads to

$$2\Gamma(\ell_0+2)\Gamma(\ell'_0+1)a_{10}^{(0)} = 1 + \ell_0 - \frac{\langle V^2 \rangle}{2T_t(r)/m}. \quad [10]$$

53 The equation above makes evident the convenient choice $\ell_0 = 0$, for which Eq. (10) yields

$$2\Gamma(\ell'_0+1)a_{10}^{(0)} = 1 - \frac{\langle V^2 \rangle}{2T_t/m} = 0, \quad \Rightarrow \quad a_{10}^{(0)} = 0, \quad [11]$$

since the definition of average translational kinetic energy T_t in Eq. (3) implies that $(m/2)\langle V^2 \rangle = T_t$. We proceed analogously to obtain $a_{01}^{(0)} = 0$ for $\ell'_0 = 0$.

Moreover, the choice $\ell_0, \ell'_0 = 0$ implies that all $a_{j,k}^{(\ell)} = 0$ except for the zeroth order contribution $a_{00}^{(0)}$, if the particle distribution function is a 2D Maxwellian (i.e., $f = f_{2M}$). Therefore, these constants (usually called cumulants or Sonine coefficients in the context of kinetic theory (4)) measure deviations from the Maxwellian (i.e., from the thermodynamic equilibrium state).

Thus, the expansion series for our distribution function would write as

$$f(r, \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{W}) = f_{2M}(r, V, W) \sum_{j,k,\ell=0}^{\infty} a_{jk}^{(\ell)} L_j^{(\ell)}(V^{*2}) L_k^{(\ell)}(W^{*2}) (\pi^{1/2} W^*) (V^{*2} W^{*2})^\ell P_\ell(\cos \alpha). \quad [12]$$

Notice that for $\ell_0, \ell'_0 = 0$ the first three associated Laguerre polynomials are $L_0^{(\ell)}(x) = 1$, $L_1^{(\ell)}(x) = (1+\ell) - x$, $L_2^{(\ell)}(x) = x^2/2 - (2+\ell)x + 1$. On the other hand, the first two Legendre polynomials are $P_0(y) = 1$, $P_1(y) = y$. Thus, by replacing $x \rightarrow V^{*2}$, W^{*2} and $y \rightarrow \cos \alpha$ and repeating the procedure in Eq. (9), Eq. (10) for the polynomial combinations $L_2^{(0)}(V^{*2})L_0^{(0)}(W^{*2})P_0(\cos \alpha)$, $L_0^{(0)}(V^{*2})L_2^{(0)}(W^{*2})P_0(\cos \alpha)$, $L_1^{(0)}(V^{*2})L_1^{(0)}(W^{*2})P_0(\cos \alpha)$ and $L_0^{(1)}(V^{*2})L_0^{(1)}(W^{*2})P_1(\cos \alpha)$ we obtain, respectively, the first four cumulants

$$a_{20}^{(0)}(r) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle V^4 \rangle}{\langle V^2 \rangle^2} - 1 \right), \quad a_{02}^{(0)}(r) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle W^4 \rangle}{\langle W^2 \rangle^2} - 1 \right), \quad a_{11}^{(0)}(r) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\langle V^2 W^2 \rangle}{\langle V^2 \rangle \langle W^2 \rangle} - 1 \right), \quad a_{00}^{(1)}(r) = \frac{3}{2} \left\langle \frac{\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{w} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_\phi}{|\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{w}|} \right\rangle, \quad [13]$$

where for the expression of $a_{00}^{(1)}$ we have taken into account our definition $\cos \alpha \equiv \langle (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{w}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_\phi / |\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{w}| \rangle$.

The cumulant $a_{00}^{(1)}$ characterizes particle translation-spin correlations. However, notice that for characterization of particle translation-spin correlations we use instead the slightly different coefficient $a_{00}^{(b)}$

$$a_{00}^{(b)} = \frac{3}{2} \langle (\mathbf{v}^* \times \mathbf{w}^*) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_\phi \rangle, \quad [14]$$

(with $\mathbf{v}^* \equiv \mathbf{v}/\sqrt{\langle V^2 \rangle}$ and $\mathbf{w}^* \equiv \mathbf{w}/\sqrt{\langle W^2 \rangle}$) which retains analogous statistical information on the relative orientation of particle translations and spin, while holding a closer analogy to the bend coefficient used in elasticity theory (5). For this reason, we used $a_{00}^{(b)}$ to characterize translation-spin correlations in Figure 4 (a) in the main file.

Supplementary figures and experiments movies

In this work we have recorded a total 120 movies covering a wide range of densities, going from $\phi = 0.03$ to $\phi = 0.70$. We could not represent all our results in the main text; therefore, here we include additional figures, complementary movies and experimental data.

- **Additional figures:** The first supplementary figure is analog to Figure 1 in the main text, covering the $\phi = 0.55$ density case, in this figure one can see that the bimodal behavior of the spin distribution function is stronger than in the lower density case (shown in the main text). Also, from panels **c-j** we now see that particle cover the entire area of the system. The second supplementary figure includes data for the cumulants defined in Eq. 2 (main text) that are not covered by Figure 4 in the article.
- **Supplementary movies:** We included two additional videos in order to help the reader understand the most relevant results. In supplementary video 1, we show three configurations with constant density but an increasing thermalization level ($T_t = \{0.63, 1.16, 2.65\} m_p(\sigma/s)^2$), this movie illustrate the chirality reversal caused by interaction with the system boundaries, we display the trajectories of three representative particles for each case. Supplementary video 2 in turn displays the temporal evolution of the vorticity field for a sample experiment, there we show a situation of complex chirality with several vortexes of opposite directions, these vortexes evolve with time.

Data availability

The data that support the plots within this paper and other findings of this study are available in the following web link: <https://zenodo.org/record/4756796>.

Codes availability

The particle tracking codes that were used for this work are available in the following web link: <https://github.com/fvegar/blades>.

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Additional Figure 1. **a** Translational particle velocity distribution (v), $f_{r,w}(v)$ for a system with $\phi = 0.55$; **b** particle spin distribution (w), $f_{r,v}(w)$. **c-f** Reduced particle speed fluctuations $U^*(x, y) \equiv v_{\text{th}}(x, y)/V_0$. **g-j** Reduced average spin $\Omega^*(x, y) \equiv \langle w(x, y) \rangle / w_0$. In both $U^*(x, y)$ and $\Omega^*(x, y)$ color maps, brighter is higher and darker is lower; and black stands for $U^*(x, y), \Omega^*(x, y) = 0$ and white for $U^*(x, y), \Omega^*(x, y) = 1$. T_t is in units of $m_p \sigma^2 / s^2$. The system boundary is marked with a thick yellow line.

Additional Figure 2. In this figure we plot the cumulants $a_{20}^{(0)}$ (blue, Y axis at the left), $a_{02}^{(0)}$ (red, Y axis at the right in logarithmic scale) for the spin and velocity distributions. Each point represents the value for a single experiment, we show that, besides the systems being clearly not Maxwellian (values far from zero), there is no clear trend in their value as we change the thermalization level.